

POLITICAL SCIENCES

NEW SCENARIOS FOR CLIMATE CHANGE ANALYSIS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION: IMPACT AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

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Abstract

It is obvious that at present, without a systematic approach, it is impossible to ensure effective protection of the EU from climate change and an environmental safety system. The established and developing modern system of environmental protection and environmental management in the European Union includes a number of specific tools based on research methods at the national level. These include: legislative, informational, administrative, economic and environmental methods. It should be noted that all of the above and constantly improving management methods complement each other, and their integrated application in practice forms the basis of the EU environmental policy in the transition from the concept to the strategy of sustainable development. Climate change, once considered exclusively an "environmental problem," is being implemented as an integral part of national and international security programs. Climate change can affect security in several ways. Often, the growing competition for access to natural resources becomes a symbol of violence if effective dispute resolution mechanisms are not created. An increase in the frequency of extreme climatic weather events and natural disasters can exacerbate political instability and threaten livelihoods, which, in turn, can force people to migrate on a large scale or switch to the production of illegal sources of income. Disruption of food production and rising food prices lead to social instability and civil unrest. Reduced energy production efficiency caused by high temperatures and falling precipitation, as well as threats to energy production and transmission infrastructure from extreme weather events have a negative impact on the supply chain and energy security. Therefore, an acute formation of new scenarios for the analysis of EU climate change is required.

Keywords: European Union, climate change, environmental problem, international security, development strategy.

Introduction

Climate change is a reality. The European Union is a leader in world climate policy and in many ways an important player. Today, the European Union has managed to reduce CO₂ emissions by 19% compared to the level of 1990, which fundamentally distinguishes the EU from other major air pollutants: in the United States, the volume of emissions increased by 8%, and in China - by 189% (climatic neutrality...2019:6-10). The main features of the EU climate policy:

- Priority of climate policy in the EU course;
- increased integration into the European strategy;
- regular update;
- powerful public support;
- priority of a single policy in the separation of powers between the EU and member countries in decision-making matters;
- Intensity of international activity and leadership in the negotiation process (EU Climate Policy Tracker, 2011:55);

The EU is trying to solve the problem of increasing its competitive advantages by pursuing an active climate policy. Undoubtedly, such activities are associated with significant investments in the short and medium term, but the result is an increase in the effectiveness of such a policy, economic growth, stimulation of innovation activities, as well as strengthening the EU's positions in the world market of low-carbon technologies.

Climate policy refers to the combined competence of the EU member states as 245 integration associations. A number of legislative acts adopted at the EU level are mandatory. These include, for example, air pollution standards. The general political directions for the development of the EU until 2020 were identified in 2007 among the strategic goals, including climate protection: ensuring a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 20% from the level of 1990; increasing the share of energy from renewable sources to 20% of final consumption; an increase in energy efficiency by 20% is envisaged (climatic neutrality...2019:12-18). In 2014, the European Council approved the main directions of climate and energy policy until 2030. "It is assumed that on the basis of the developed strategic directions, the European Union will be able to make a unified and ambitious proposal at the global climate conference in Paris in December 2015." The basis of the 2030 strategy was the targets for reducing carbon emissions, improving energy efficiency, as well as reforming the carbon emissions sales system. By 2030, the European Council formulated the main tasks as follows:

- reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by 40% compared to the level of 1990 (mandatory goal);
- increase the share of renewable energy to 27% in the EU energy balance (mandatory target);
- increase energy efficiency by 27% (Piskulova N. A., 2010:120);

As for the goal of increasing the share of energy from renewable energy sources to 27% by 2030, it is assumed that it will be mandatory for the European Union as a single integration organization as a whole. The EU regulations do not establish differentiated targets for EU member states. All 27 countries of the Union must assume obligations within the framework of national legal systems in order to jointly timely fulfill a common obligation for the EU. Undoubtedly, significant changes were required to the directive 2009/28/EU " on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable energy sources " (Framework Convention..., 2015).

Speaking about the EU as a climate leader, it should be noted that there are disagreements within the union that hinder the ambitious goals of the EU. Traditional problems for the European Union, such as the division of the participating countries into "new" and "Old" Europe, are also observed when making climate decisions. For example, during the negotiations on the "Strategy 2030", the countries of the Union were clearly divided into two groups. Germany, France, Belgium, Denmark, Spain, Finland, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Slovenia, Estonia, on the one hand, are the countries that supported the objectives of the strategy. On the other hand, countries such as Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary Slovakia, Bulgaria, Romania insisted that climate policy should not undermine the competitiveness of national economies. Countries have suggested waiting at least until the results of the 2015 climate summit. On the example of the strategy adopted until 2030, it can be said that the "New Europe" won (climatic neutrality..., 2019:17-18).

In order to access cheap energy, the European Union accordingly reduces its ambitions in the climate sector. This is another important EU task in determining climate policy. It is clear that climate policy requires large investments from the EU. However, given the economic problems, as well as budgetary constraints, this fact poses a big problem. In addition, climate initiatives can be an economic constraint for EU member states. The implementation of such initiatives can reduce the competitive advantages of European companies.

Climate change is a big problem for Europeans. According to the results of a European survey published in September 2020, 9 out of 10 citizens (92 %) consider climate change to be an important issue (Reuters, 2021:10). According to the researchers' report, over the past two decades, the weather has shown a minimum thermal temperature and observed an increase in extreme frequency and intensity. Climate-related emergencies such as forest fires, floods, typhoons and hurricanes cause massive destruction and human casualties, as well as economic losses. In 2019-2020, global economic losses due to natural disasters caused by atmospheric conditions amounted to 283 billion euros. According to a report published in October 2020 by the intergovernmental group on climate change, the planet is warming by 0.2 °C every decade, the global temperature has already risen by 1 °C, and if we do not act, it has announced a forecast that it could reach 2 °C by 2060 (Reuters..., 2021:15-20). If this happens, the

consequences of climate change around the world will be dire. For example, the disappearance of 99% of coral reefs, and the loss of the Greenland ice sheet can lead to an increase in sea level by 7 meters, which will radically affect coastal areas. All this has serious consequences for the European and global economy, infrastructure, food production, Public Health, Biological Diversity and political stability. According to statistics, it is estimated that by 2100 the annual damage from floods in Europe could increase from 5 billion euros to 112 billion euros, and 16% of the current Mediterranean climate zone could become desert. In addition, the decline in food availability will significantly decrease by 2 °C compared to 1.5 °C during global warming. Only by limiting the increase in global temperature to 1.5 °C can the world avoid some of the worst effects of climate change and reduce the likelihood of weather emergencies (EU global..., 2015:250). Thus, urgent and decisive measures are needed to prevent climate change.

How to achieve long-term goals in terms of temperature in climate change?

- achieving a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions from 80% to 100% compared to 1990, the last indicator corresponds to the climate - neutral economy of the EU by 2050 (climatic neutrality..., 2019:15-17).;

- to build on policies that will not cause regret in the future, such as actively striving for energy efficiency and not only the use of renewable energy sources, but also to change the intensity of the distribution of electrification, hydrogen and synthetic fuels, as well as to improve the energy consumption efficiency of end users and the role of a waste-free economy;

- to show that the EU's thriving economy is compatible with ambitious climate goals even in the face of existing technologies;

European Society and the system: a strategy for influence and further development

The regulatory framework necessary for the formation of a climate-free society based on the European Union includes a set of political measures to implement changes and at the same time guarantees public recognition and remains socially fair. It will cover such key areas of formation of EU society and economy as climate change, the use of digital technologies, resource efficiency.

Financial capital:

The European Commission proposed to put climate issues first, increasing the share allocated to the EU's future budget for 2021-2027 by 25%, noting that EU spending will remain a stimulating factor for attracting private and public investment, and will direct EU support towards the transition to clean energy-based technologies. This ensures that the EU's spending on various programs, such as Horizon Europe (European Horizon), European Structural and investment funds, unified Agricultural Policy and InvestEU, will contribute to the investments necessary to implement the climate goals. In addition, the Innovation Development Fund, which brings together resources from the European system of trade in greenhouse gas quotas (EU ETC), supports low-carbon technologies in several ar-

eas, such as energy-intensive industries, renewable energy sources, carbon capture, utilization and energy storage (Horizon Europe..., 2021). The financial sector plays an important role in redirecting capital flows and investments. The European Commission's action plan on a sustainable financial system combines finance and the EU's sustainable development course. For example, the commission's proposal to create a unified classification system is aimed at identifying environmentally friendly economic activities and increasing transparency for investors.

Impact on the economy and social sphere:

In 2050, the economy and Society of Europe will be completely different (European Union to the global role..., 2015:302). Modern demographics note an increase in the percentage of aging of society, which can lead to a complication of the stability of public finances. In addition, the society must be well equipped to work with information and communication technologies. In a dynamic world where we interact and do business, our economy requires serious modernization and decisive action to maintain competitiveness, re-industrialize and restore leadership in technology. Massive investments are needed to ensure the success of Europe in the 21st century, modernize cities and improve the quality of life of citizens.

In Europe, about four million jobs are associated with ecology. The policy of implementing the EU energy goals has ensured the growth of the working population by 1-1.5% by 2020 and the transition to a climate - neutral economy will give an impetus to further employment growth. The policy of the EU Energy Union, including the new goals set for 2030, is expected to create new high-quality jobs, taking into account the established needs for investment in industrial modernization, energy transformation, circular economy, green and blue infrastructure (climatic neutrality..., 2019:18). Although job opportunities improve in some sectors, such as construction or renewable energy, some regions may suffer if they depend on declining or changing activities, such as coal mining or oil and gas field exploration. Other jobs require restructuring and adaptation to this new economy. In addition, the transition occurs in the context of a dwindling and aging workforce, as well as in the context of the transfer of Labor to automation due to technological changes.

This modernization process requires quality management to ensure a fair and socially acceptable transition for all in the spirit of tolerance and cooperation. The EU and member countries must take into account the social consequences and implement appropriate policies to mitigate them.

European influence:

International cooperation will be the key to the successful leadership of the EU in the transition to a low-carbon economy. The EU should promote the adoption of policies and measures aimed at reversing current atmospheric emissions, as well as managing the transition to low carbon consumption around the world. According to the European Development consensus, the EU will use its foreign economic activity, Trade Policy and international cooperation to support the

global transition to low-carbon sustainable development paths. Private and global rule-based trade can contribute to the global transition to climate-friendly technologies, promote changes in energy and help provide the necessary raw materials, including those used in low-carbon technologies. The EU is the largest single market in the world and the influence of European environmental standards is spreading outside the EU. Access to markets, infrastructure and the right to essential raw materials from partner countries must be achieved so that the EU does not remain an open platform without climatically harmful investment and trade (Gusev A. A., 2010:26).

This calls for the expansion of EU diplomacy on energy and climate, as well as the further promotion of climate change goals and considerations in political dialogues, including in the areas of cooperation in migration, security and development.

Conclusion

It must be understood that climate change poses a global threat, and Europe cannot fight it alone. Therefore, cooperation with partner countries is necessary. In addition, the EU has an unwavering interest in working to achieve an economy with zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 and proving that it is compatible with prosperity in order to encourage other countries to follow this pattern (the EU..., 2015:402). This represents a great opportunity to make efforts to strategically overcome the challenges of the 21st century. The purpose of this strategic concept is to form a specific direction.

In the formation of climate security, the main role in its development is played by man. The transition to an environmentally sustainable economy depends not only on technologies and jobs, but primarily on people, their lifestyle, interaction.

Consumers are given an important role in promoting transformation. Any choice of an individual affects ecology. Lifestyle choices provide a significant opportunity to move to climate neutrality, improving the quality of life. Cities are laboratories for transformational and sustainable solutions. Urban modernization and spatial planning can be the driving force behind the renovation of homes and drive many people to live closer to the place of work, improve living conditions, reduce travel time and The Associated stress. In addition, it will be necessary to create a public infrastructure that can withstand the consequences of climate change. The EU should have the role of Regions, Cities and towns and should expand this role. It is only a matter of time before the climate and energy agreement of the governors becomes an example of a cooperation platform created on behalf of 200 million Europeans and allowing local governments to learn from each other (EU, ... 2011:228).

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